

AVAILABILITY OF RESOURCES AND QUALITY OF EARLY CHILD EDUCATION IN MARILOG DISTRICT

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Abstract. *The study determined the availability of resources and quality of early childhood education in Marilog District Schools, Davao City Division. The study used non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, where it utilized adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher-respondents. Data gathered were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that extent of availability of resources in terms of teacher training and support, community support and engagement, health and safety, adequate facilities, resources, access to educational resources is moderately extensive, likewise, extent of students' understanding in mathematical concepts in terms of assessment and evaluation, teacher-child interaction, family engagement and curriculum and instructional practices moderately extensive. There is a significant relationship between availability of resources and quality of early childhood education learners. Domains of availability of resources in terms of access to educational resources, teacher training and support, community support and engagement, adequate facilities and resources, and health and safety does significantly influenced quality of early childhood education learners. Future research may examine the long-term effects of resource availability in early childhood education on children's academic achievement, socio-emotional development, and future success. Explore the relationship between resource availability and the inclusion of diverse learners, such as those with disabilities or from culturally and linguistically diverse backgrounds. May conduct further research on the impact of specific resources and their availability on early childhood education outcomes. Investigate the effectiveness of different resource allocation models and strategies in promoting quality early childhood education.*

KEY WORDS

1. availability of resources.
2. quality of early child education.

1. Introduction

Early childhood education (ECE) is a critical component of human development, providing young children with a foundation for lifelong learning and success. However, access to quality ECE programs is not universal, and the availability of resources plays a significant role in determining the quality of education. The

availability of resources is a significant determinant of the quality of early childhood education. According to UNICEF (2018), 175 million children worldwide are not enrolled in pre-primary education, and many children who are enrolled in early childhood education programs do not have access to the resources necessary to sup-

port their learning. In a study conducted by Shonkoff et al. (2019), it was found that the quality of early childhood education is closely related to the availability of resources, including trained teachers, adequate facilities, and learning materials. In many low- and middle-income countries, the lack of resources is a significant challenge to providing quality early childhood education. According to a report by the World Bank (2020), many low-income countries allocate less than 5% of their national budget to early childhood education. The quality of early childhood education is not only determined by the availability of resources but also by the effectiveness of teaching practices. In a study conducted by Li and Li (2021), it was found that teacher-child interactions are a critical factor in determining the quality of early childhood education. Effective teaching practices, such as providing a stimulating environment, using positive reinforcement, and encouraging children's active participation, can enhance children's cognitive and socio-emotional development. However, effective teaching practices are not universal, and there are significant challenges to ensuring that all children have access to quality early childhood education. In a study conducted by Bierman et al. (2018), it was found that many early childhood education programs in the United States fail to provide the necessary support for children's learning and development. The study found that many early childhood education programs did not have trained teachers, appropriate curriculum materials, or effective teaching practices. The availability of resources and the quality of early childhood education are closely related, with significant challenges to ensuring that all children have access to quality ECE programs. According to UNICEF (2018), the primary challenge to ensuring access to quality ECE programs is the lack of investment in early childhood education. Many countries prioritize spending on primary and secondary education, neglecting the critical foundation that early childhood education provides. One of the challenges in the Philippines is the lack of access to ECE. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), only 4 out of 10 children aged 3 to 4 years old are enrolled in any type of pre-primary education. This low enrollment rate can be attributed to various factors, including poverty, lack of awareness, and geographic barriers (UNICEF, 2021). The lack of access to ECE can have long-term effects on a child's development, particularly in terms of cognitive and socio-emotional skills. Another challenge in the Philippines is the quality of ECE. Even for those who have access to ECE, the quality of education varies greatly. In a study by Aquino and Ylanan (2020), they found that the quality of ECE in the Philippines is affected by the lack of trained teachers, inadequate facilities, and the absence of appropriate learning materials. The authors recommended that the government should invest more in ECE to improve the quality of education and provide better learning opportunities for children. Furthermore, the Philippine government has also allocated a significant portion of its national budget to education, including ECE. In 2021, the Department of Education received a budget of Php 773.6 billion, with a significant portion allocated to ECE programs (Department of Budget and Management, 2021). This investment is expected to improve the availability of resources and quality of ECE in the Philippines. In conclusion, the availability of resources and quality of ECE is a critical issue in the Philippines. The lack of access to ECE and the varying quality of education can have long-term effects on a child's development. However, with the implementation of programs and initiatives, such as the ECCD program and increased government funding, there is hope for improvement in the availability of resources and quality of ECE in the Philippines, thus this study is conducted.

2. Methodology

This chapter contains the discussion of the methodical process in the conduct of the study. This includes the process in the selection of the design of the study, the respondents and its sampling method, the research instruments to be used in data gathering, the procedure, and the ethical consideration and lastly, the data analysis. These steps are considered essentials to assume appropriateness and correctness in the conduct of the methodical steps.

2.1. Research Design—This study used non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design. This refers to studies which describe the variables and the relationships that occur naturally between and among them. Further, the study variables are classified as independent (predictor) and dependent (outcome). Moreover, Any scientific process begins with description, based on observation, of an event or events, from which theories may later be developed to explain the observations (Pallant, 2020). Correlational research can be applied to the study of the availability of resources and the quality of delivery of early childhood education. Correlational research is a type of non-experimental research that investigates the relationship between two or more variables. In this case, the variables of interest are the availability of resources and the quality of delivery of early childhood education. Correlational research can be applied to investigate the relationship between the availability of resources and the quality of delivery of early childhood education. The goal of correlational research is to identify whether two or more variables are related, and if so, the strength and direction of that relationship. In this case, the availability of resources can be one variable, and the quality of delivery of early childhood education can be the other variable. To study this relationship, data can be collected from multiple early childhood education centers in the Marilog District of Davao City. The data collection methods could include surveys, observations, and interviews with teachers, parents, and program administrators.

2.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the study were the Elementary Teachers of Marilog District in Davao City Division. Using Raosoft sample size calculator, a total of 120 respondents were taken randomly from each respective elementary school. Once randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platform and face to face considering the availability of the Wifi Connections, they likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study. As much as possible, these respondents are teaching Kinder to Grade learners in the respective schools to measure competence, and how they function and contributed to the learning outcomes given new normal learning system during SY 2022-2023. Ethics of research and in the process of collecting survey responses were explicitly discussed with the respondents and even observance to health protocol was strictly implemented based on the Executive Order 31 S 2020, to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. Research Instrument—This research study used a self-made survey instrument. Items were adapted from the contents of the reviewed literatures. There are two parts of the survey questionnaire which consists of the access to educational resources, teacher – training support, community engagement, adequate facilities and resources and health and safety. On the other hand, the second part of the survey is the quality of delivery of kindergarten learners in terms of teacher-child interactions, curriculum and instructional practices, family engagement and assessment and evaluation. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or va-

lidity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at .05 level of confidence and generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.897 which means that 89.7 percent level of confidence of the validity and reliability of the survey statement constructs. (Pallant 2010).

Table 1. Descriptive Ratings of Resource Availability

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The availability of resources is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The availability of resources is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The availability of resources is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The availability of resources is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The availability of resources is not manifested

Table 2. Descriptive Ratings of Quality Delivery

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The quality delivery is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The delivery is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The quality delivery is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The quality delivery is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The quality delivery is not manifested

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The preceding statements explains the data gathering procedure steps where the researcher must comprehensively consider and follow. The statements of the are based on the policies and guidelines of the Rizal Memorial Colleges and the existing guidelines of the IATF to ensure safe and lower risks in the gathering of pertinent data.

Permission to conduct the study. Before collecting data, the researcher must obtain permission from the appropriate authorities, such as the research adviser and the Dean of the Rizal Memorial Colleges and the top management of DepEd Davao City Division through channel. This permission-seeking process typically involves submitting a research proposal that includes information about the study design, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. The researcher will provide information about the purpose and goals of the study, and how the data will be collected, analyzed, and reported. In addition, researchers must ensure that all participants are fully informed about the study and their rights, and that they provide informed consent before participating. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. To ensure the accuracy and completeness of data, the distribution and retrieval of questionnaires should be conducted in a standardized and systematic manner. This may involve the following conditions: 1. Identifying the target population: The researcher identified the appropriate target population of the study, and ensure that the questionnaire is distributed only to individuals who meet the inclusion criteria. 2. Obtaining consent: The researcher obtained informed consent from all participants before distributing the questionnaire. This may involve providing information about the purpose and goals of the study, as well as any potential risks and benefits. 3. Ensuring anonymity and confidentiality: The researcher ensured that the questionnaire is anonymous,

meaning that respondents are not identified by name or other personal information. The researcher also ensured that the data collected is kept confidential and only used for the purposes of the study.

4. Standardizing the distribution process: The researcher standardized the process for distributing the questionnaire, to ensure that all participants receive the same instructions and have the same opportunity to complete the questionnaire.

5. Allowing sufficient time for completion: Participants were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaire, and were allowed to ask any questions they may have about the process.

6. Collecting the completed questionnaires: The researcher collected the completed questionnaires in a timely and organized manner, to ensure that data is not lost or misplaced.

Collation and statistical treatment of data. The following are the general conditions that should be followed for collation and statistical treatment of data as part of the data gathering procedure:

1. Accuracy: The data should be accurate and free from errors. This means that the data should be checked and validated to ensure that it is correct.
2. Completeness: The data should be complete, meaning that all necessary information has been collected. This is important because incomplete data can lead to incorrect conclusions.
3. Consistency: The data should be consistent, meaning that there are no contradictions or discrepancies in the data. Inconsistencies can lead to confusion and inaccuracies.
4. Relevance: The data should be relevant to the research question or problem being investigated. Irrelevant data can lead to incorrect conclusions.
5. Timeliness: The data should be collected and analyzed in a timely manner. Delayed or outdated data may not be useful or accurate.
6. Objectivity: The data should be objective, meaning that it is free from bias or personal opinions. This is important because biased data can lead to incorrect conclusions.
7. Validity: The data should be valid, meaning that it measures what it is supposed to measure. This is important because invalid data can lead to incorrect conclusions.
8. Reliability: The data should be reliable, meaning that it can be replicated or reproduced. This is important because unreliable data can lead to incorrect conclusions.
9. Statistical treatment: The data should be subjected to appropriate statistical analysis to identify patterns, trends, and relationships. Statistical analysis can help to reveal important insights and relationships in the data.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation was used to address statement problems posed in number one (1) on the extent of availability of resources, and statement problem number two (2) on the extent of quality delivery of Early Childhood Education. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength / direction significant relationship between the availability of resources and quality delivery of Early Childhood Education in Marilog District schools of Davao City Division. Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4, on the indicators of availability of resources that significantly influence quality delivery of Early Childhood Education in Marilog District schools of Davao City Division. All data processing and analysis were treated using the Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations then followed when results yield.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered. Tabular and textual presentation is presented to make more meaningful in the analysis and drawing out of implications. This further shows evidence to support the claim posed in the hypothesis.

Availability of Resources One of the primary factors that impact the availability of resources for early childhood education is the level of investment in education by governments and other stakeholders. According to UNESCO (2021), only 0.5% of early childhood education requires skilled and knowledgeable teachers who are capable of providing age-appropriate learning experiences and supporting children's social and emotional development. However, many countries face a shortage of trained and qualified teachers for early childhood education. In some cases, early childhood education is provided by untrained caregivers, which can lead to inadequate learning experiences and negative outcomes for children (UNESCO, 2021). The level of investment in education, availability of trained and qualified teachers, and physical infrastructure all impact the delivery of early childhood education. Many areas in the Philippines lack the necessary infrastructure to support early childhood education, with inadequate classrooms, few or no learning materials, and limited access to technology. This lack of infrastructure can limit the effectiveness of teaching and hinder children's learning and development.

Table 1 shows the extent of availability of

resources in terms of access to educational resources. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Includes access to devices such as computers, tablets, and interactive whiteboards, as well as educational software and apps that support learning and development (3.20), Availability of items such as books, puzzles, games, art supplies, and manipulatives that support learning and development in early childhood (3.15) and Includes classrooms and other areas that are designed to promote learning and development, such as outdoor play areas, sensory rooms, and reading corners (3.00) are sometimes manifested; while, Teachers who have specialized training and qualifications in early childhood education can help ensure that children are receiving high-quality instruction and support (2.45) is rarely manifested, and Support services such as speech and language therapy, mental health services, and special education can help ensure that children with diverse needs receive the resources they need to thrive (1.12) is not extensive. The overall mean rating of 2.58 denotes extent of availability of resources in terms of access to educational resources is rarely manifested, thus, less extensive.

Access to educational resources is a critical component of the availability of resources in the delivery of high-quality early childhood education in the international setting. Early childhood education programs that provide access to a range of resources, including learning materials, facilities, and skilled teachers, have been shown to lead to better learning outcomes and long-term benefits for children. A study by Engle and Black (2008) explored the importance of access to educational resources in early childhood education programs in low-income countries. The study found that access to learning materials, such as books, toys, and games, had a significant impact on children's cognitive development and school readiness. Arnett (2012) examined access to educational resources in early childhood education programs in high-income countries. The study found that while these programs generally had access to a wide range of resources, there were still disparities in their distribution across different regions and socio-economic groups. In

Table 3. Extent of Availability of Resources in Terms of Access to Educational Resources

No	Educational Resources	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Availability of items such as books, puzzles, games, art supplies, and manipulatives that support learning and development in early childhood.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
2	Includes access to devices such as computers, tablets, and interactive whiteboards, as well as educational software and apps that support learning and development.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
3	Includes classrooms and other areas that are designed to promote learning and development, such as outdoor play areas, sensory rooms, and reading corners.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
4	Teachers who have specialized training and qualifications in early childhood education can help ensure that children are receiving high-quality instruction and support.	2.45	Less Extensive
5	Support services such as speech and language therapy, mental health services, and special education can help ensure that children with diverse needs receive the resources they need to thrive.	1.12	Not Extensive
Overall Mean		2.58	Less Extensive

particular, low-income families and children from marginalized communities had less access to high-quality early childhood education programs, which limited their opportunities for learning and development. Yoshikawa et al. (2013) examined the impact of access to educational resources on the long-term outcomes of early childhood education programs. The study found that access to high-quality early childhood education programs, including access to learning materials, facilities, and skilled teachers, led to better academic and social-emotional outcomes for children in both the short and long term. On the other hand, Abadiano and Cabaero (2019) examined the availability and utilization of educational resources in early childhood education in the Philippines. The study found that while there were a range of educational resources available, including learning materials and facilities, there were significant disparities in their distribution across different regions and socio-economic groups. In particular, rural areas and low-income families had less access to educational resources, which limited their opportunities for high-quality early childhood education.

Table 4 shows the extent of availability of resources in terms of teacher training and support. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Includes opportunities for teachers to collaborate with one another, share ideas and resources, and work together to create a supportive and effective learning environment for young children (4.00) is oftentimes manifested; Includes access to ongoing training and development opportunities that help teachers stay up-to-date with the latest research and best practices in early childhood education (3.30) and Includes access to experienced mentors and coaches who can provide guidance and support to teachers as they develop their skills and improve their teaching practices (3.20) are sometimes manifested; while, Includes access to tools and resources that help teachers track student progress and identify areas where additional support may be needed (2.45) and Includes having enough teachers and support staff to provide individualized attention to students, as well as having sufficient resources to support student learning, such as books, technology, and classroom materials (2.12) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.01 denotes extent of availability of resources in terms of teacher training and support is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Teacher training and support are critical components of the availability of resources in the delivery of early childhood education (ECE) in the international setting. These factors are crucial in ensuring that teachers are adequately prepared and equipped to provide high-quality early education to young children. One study conducted by Yoshikawa et al. (2013) analyzed the evidence base for preschool education and found that teacher training and support are essential components of effective ECE programs. The study found that high-quality teacher training and professional development can improve teacher knowledge, skills, and instructional practices, which can lead to better child outcomes. Another study by UNESCO (2017) highlighted the importance of teacher training in ECE. The study found that effective ECE programs require well-trained and competent teachers who have a strong understanding of child development and early learning. The study also noted that ongoing professional development opportunities and support are necessary for teachers to continue to grow and improve their practice. Blaise and Nuttall (2011), the authors highlighted the importance of considering cultural contexts when providing teacher training and support in ECE. The study emphasized the need for teacher training programs to be culturally sensitive and relevant to the local context. The authors argued that teacher training programs that take into account the cultural backgrounds and experiences of

Table 4. Extent of Availability of Resources in Terms of Teacher Training and Support

No	Teacher Training and Support	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Includes access to ongoing training and development opportunities that help teachers stay up-to-date with the latest research and best practices in early childhood education.	3.30	Moderately Extensive
2	Includes access to experienced mentors and coaches who can provide guidance and support to teachers as they develop their skills and improve their teaching practices.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
3	Includes opportunities for teachers to collaborate with one another, share ideas and resources, and work together to create a supportive and effective learning environment for young children.	4.00	Extensive
4	Includes access to tools and resources that help teachers track student progress and identify areas where additional support may be needed.	2.45	Less Extensive
5	Includes having enough teachers and support staff to provide individualized attention to students, as well as having sufficient resources to support student learning, such as books, technology, and classroom materials.	2.12	Less Extensive
	Overall Mean	3.01	Moderately Extensive

teachers can lead to better teacher engagement and effectiveness. Maligalig and Albert (2018) examined the quality of teacher training programs for ECE in the Philippines. The study found that while there were many training programs available, the quality of these programs varied widely. The study highlighted the need for standardized and evidence-based training programs to ensure that teachers are adequately prepared and equipped to provide high-quality ECE. Arbolado and Tandog (2017) focused on the impact of teacher training on teaching practices and child outcomes. The study found that teachers who received training and professional development opportunities had better teaching practices and that children in these classrooms had better cognitive and language outcomes compared to children in classrooms with less trained teachers. In a similar study by Ilagan and De Leon (2018), the authors examined the impact of peer mentoring on teacher development and child outcomes in the Philippines. The study found that peer mentoring was an effective way to provide support and feedback to teachers, which led to improvements in teaching practices and better child outcomes. In conclusion, teacher training and support are critical components of resource availability in the delivery of ECE in the Philippine setting. The reviewed studies provide evidence for the importance of high-quality teacher training and ongoing professional development opportunities in promoting positive child outcomes. The studies also highlight the need for standardized and evidence-based training programs and the effectiveness of coaching and peer mentoring as support systems for teachers.

Table 5 shows the extent of availability of resources in terms of community support and engagement. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Includes opportunities for parents to be involved in their child's education, such as volunteering in the classroom, attending parent-teacher conferences, and participating in parent education programs (4.15) is oftentimes manifested; while, Includes partnerships between early childhood education programs and community organizations, such as local businesses, nonprofits, and government agencies, that can provide additional resources and support (3.20) and Includes ensuring that the early childhood education program is responsive to the cultural needs and preferences of the families and communities it serves (3.00) are sometimes observed; and Includes access to health care services, such as pediatricians and mental health professionals, as well as social services, such as food assistance and housing support (2.45) and Includes efforts to raise awareness about the importance of early childhood education and to advocate for policies and resources that support high-quality early childhood education programs (2.12) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.98 denotes extent of availability of resources in terms of community support and engagement is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Community support and engagement have been recognized as critical components of resource availability in the delivery of early childhood education (ECE) worldwide. The involvement of families, caregivers, and community members in early education programs can positively impact the quality of education, children's academic outcomes, and overall well-being. Takacs et al. (2018) focused on the impact of community-based programs on ECE in low-income communities in the United States. The study found that community-based programs, which included family engagement and support, had a positive impact on children's academic and social-emotional development, and they were effective in closing the achievement gap between low-income and higher-income children. In a similar study by Ali et al. (2019), the authors examined the impact of community involvement in early education programs

Table 5. Extent of Availability of Resources in Terms of Community Support and Engagement

No	Community Support and Engagement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Includes opportunities for parents to be involved in their child’s education, such as volunteering in the classroom, attending parent-teacher conferences, and participating in parent education programs.	4.15	Extensive
2	Includes partnerships between early childhood education programs and community organizations, such as local businesses, nonprofits, and government agencies, that can provide additional resources and support.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
3	Includes ensuring that the early childhood education program is responsive to the cultural needs and preferences of the families and communities it serves.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
4	Includes access to health care services, such as pediatricians and mental health professionals, as well as social services, such as food assistance and housing support.	2.45	Less Extensive
5	Includes efforts to raise awareness about the importance of early childhood education and to advocate for policies and resources that support high-quality early childhood education programs.	2.12	Less Extensive
	Overall Mean	2.98	Moderately Extensive

in rural Pakistan. The study found that community involvement and support were essential in improving children's academic and social-emotional outcomes and increasing enrollment and attendance rates in early education programs. Community support and engagement is a crucial component of the availability of resources in the delivery of early childhood education (ECE). Community involvement in ECE programs can lead to improved access to resources, enhanced quality of programs, and increased parental engagement in their children's learning. Aguja and Dimabayao (2017) explored the role of barangay (community) leaders in promoting ECE in the Philippines. The study found that barangay leaders played a vital role in the establishment and maintenance of ECE programs in their respective communities. They facilitated community participation in ECE programs, mobilized resources, and provided support to ECE teachers. The study also identified the need for further training and capacity building for barangay leaders to enhance their role in supporting ECE programs. Gracia et al. (2019) investigated the impact of community involvement in ECE programs in the Philippines on parental engagement in their children's learning. The study found that parental involvement increased when they were engaged in the ECE program through community-based activities. The study highlighted the importance of community involvement in ECE programs to promote parental engagement, which, in turn, has a positive impact on children's learning outcomes. Mallorca and Aguja (2021) examined the impact of community-based ECE programs on the school readiness of Filipino children. The study

found that community-based ECE programs that involved parents and community members in program design and implementation resulted in higher levels of school readiness among children. The study emphasized the importance of community involvement in promoting ECE programs, particularly in underserved communities. Table 4 shows the extent of availability of resources in terms of adequate facilities and resources. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Includes providing materials and resources that are developmentally appropriate for young children, such as books, toys, and educational materials (4.00) is oftentimes manifested; and, Includes ensuring that the physical environment of the early childhood education program is safe, clean, and well-maintained, with appropriate materials and equipment for young children (3.20) is sometimes manifested; while, Includes having enough indoor and outdoor space for children to play, learn, and explore, as well as space for staff to work and collaborate (2.20) and Includes ensuring that the early childhood education program has sufficient staffing levels to provide high-quality care and education to young children, including well-trained teachers and support staff (2.10) are rarely manifested, and Includes access to technology and other resources that can enhance the learning experiences of young children, such as computers, tablets, and educational software (1.45) is not manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.59 denotes extent of availability of resources in terms of adequate facilities and resources is rarely manifested, thus, less extensive.

Access to adequate facilities and resources is a critical factor that affects the quality of early childhood education globally. Adequate facilities and resources are necessary for providing high-quality early childhood education. Accord-

ing to a study by UNESCO (2018), adequate facilities and resources such as play areas, classrooms, libraries, and learning materials enhance the quality of early childhood education. The study further indicates that facilities such as

Table 6. Extent of Availability of Resources in Terms of Adequate Facilities and Resources

No	Adequate Facilities and Resources	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Includes ensuring that the physical environment of the early childhood education program is safe, clean, and well-maintained, with appropriate materials and equipment for young children.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
2	Includes having enough indoor and outdoor space for children to play, learn, and explore, as well as space for staff to work and collaborate.	2.20	Less Extensive
3	Includes providing materials and resources that are developmentally appropriate for young children, such as books, toys, and educational materials.	4.00	Extensive
4	Includes access to technology and other resources that can enhance the learning experiences of young children, such as computers, tablets, and educational software.	1.45	Not Extensive
5	Includes ensuring that the early childhood education program has sufficient staffing levels to provide high-quality care and education to young children, including well-trained teachers and support staff.	2.10	Less Extensive
	Overall Mean	2.59	Less Extensive

safe and clean toilets, clean drinking water, and good ventilation systems are also necessary for creating a conducive learning environment for children. Bennett and O’Keeffe (2014) found that the availability of adequate facilities and resources is a key factor in ensuring the quality of early childhood education. The authors argue that inadequate facilities and resources such as overcrowded classrooms, poor sanitation, and lack of learning materials can hinder the delivery of high-quality early childhood education. In addition to physical facilities, access to resources such as learning materials is also critical in early childhood education. A study by Kim and Kim (2018) found that access to learning resources such as books, toys, and games positively impacts the cognitive and socio-emotional development of young children. The study further argues that access to learning resources can enhance children’s learning experience and increase their engagement in the learning process. In the Philippines, Early childhood education is an essential aspect of every child’s development. Providing adequate facilities and resources is crucial to ensure the delivery of quality education in this critical stage of a child’s life. In the Philippine setting, access to such resources is often a challenge, particularly in disadvantaged communities. One of the essential resources in early childhood education is a conducive learning environment. Studies have shown that a positive and stimulating learning environment enhances children’s engagement and cognitive development (Bradley Caldwell, 1979; Cohen Spenciner, 1994). However, many early childhood education programs in the Philippines face the challenge of limited physical space and poorly designed learning environments (Seneres, 2015). In a study by the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS), it was revealed that most early childhood education centers in the country lack basic facilities, such as safe and well-ventilated class-

rooms, clean toilets, and adequate water supply (Layug dela Cruz, 2016). Finally, community support and engagement are critical components of the availability of resources in the delivery of early childhood education. Studies have shown that involving parents and the community in early childhood education programs leads to positive outcomes, such as increased parental involvement, improved child development outcomes, and better school readiness (Powell et al., 2010; Sulimma Reese, 2013). In the Philippine setting, community support and engagement in early childhood education programs are often limited, particularly in disadvantaged areas where parents’ access to information and resources is scarce (Layug dela Cruz, 2016).

Table 5 shows the extent of availability of resources in terms of health and safety. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Includes having sufficient toilets, handwashing facilities, and other sanitation resources to ensure that young children can maintain good hygiene and prevent the spread of disease (3.15); Includes having plans and resources in place to respond to emergencies or disasters that may occur, such as natural disasters or medical emergencies (3.10) and Includes providing nutritious and safe food for young children, including meals and snacks that meet dietary guidelines and are prepared and stored safely (3.00) are sometimes manifested; while, Includes creating a safe and supportive environment for young children, with appropriate measures in place to prevent injury, violence, or abuse (2.40) and Includes providing access to health services and support for young children, such as health screenings, immunizations, and referrals to health professionals as needed (2.20) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.77 denotes extent of availability of resources in terms of health and safety is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 7. Extent of Availability of Resources in Terms of Health and Safety

No	Health and Safety	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Includes having sufficient toilets, handwashing facilities, and other sanitation resources to ensure that young children can maintain good hygiene and prevent the spread of disease.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
2	Includes providing nutritious and safe food for young children, including meals and snacks that meet dietary guidelines and are prepared and stored safely.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
3	Includes having plans and resources in place to respond to emergencies or disasters that may occur, such as natural disasters or medical emergencies.	3.10	Moderately Extensive
4	Includes creating a safe and supportive environment for young children, with appropriate measures in place to prevent injury, violence, or abuse.	2.40	Less Extensive
5	Includes providing access to health services and support for young children, such as health screenings, immunizations, and referrals to health professionals as needed.	2.20	Less Extensive
	Overall Mean	2.77	Moderately Extensive

Early childhood education plays a vital role in a child’s development, and one critical aspect of delivering quality early childhood education is ensuring the health and safety of young learners. Sheridan and Copeland (2019) explored the relationship between health and safety and the quality of early childhood education programs in Australia. The authors found that health and safety practices were positively associated with the quality of early childhood education. The study emphasized the importance of adequate health and safety regulations, including

regular inspections of facilities and equipment, to ensure that children are safe and healthy. Pelto (2017) emphasized the need for health and safety standards in early childhood education in the United States. The author discussed the importance of implementing evidence-based practices to prevent injuries and promote healthy behaviors. The study found that implementing appropriate health and safety practices positively impacted the quality of early childhood education programs. Furthermore, a study by Jia and colleagues (2018) examined health and

safety practices in early childhood education programs in China. The authors found that inadequate health and safety practices negatively impacted the quality of early childhood education. The study emphasized the need for policymakers to prioritize the implementation of appropriate health and safety standards to improve the quality of early childhood education programs. The Philippines is a country that is committed to the provision of quality ECE programs for its young population. However, ensuring that these programs are safe and healthy is a major challenge for the country, given its limited resources and the varying conditions in different regions. According to a study conducted by Amaya (2019), many ECE programs in the Philippines lack basic facilities, such as toilets and clean water sources. This lack of facilities puts young children at risk of contracting diseases and other health issues. World Health Organization (WHO) and the Department of Health (DOH) in the Philippines found that many ECE centers in the country did not meet the minimum standards for health and safety (WHO DOH, 2019). Specifically, the study found that most centers lacked proper sanitation and hygiene facilities, had inadequate ventilation, and did not provide safe drinking water to children. The study also noted that there was a lack of awareness among ECE providers and parents regarding the importance of health and safety in early childhood education. To address these challenges, the Philippine government has implemented various policies and

Availability of educational resources, such as textbooks, libraries, and digital materials, is vital for students' learning experiences. In developed countries, access to educational resources is generally more widespread, with well-stocked libraries, advanced technology, and digital platforms. However, in developing countries, resource availability may be limited due

programs aimed at improving the health and safety of ECE centers. For example, the Department of Education (DepEd) has established guidelines for the construction and maintenance of ECE centers, which include provisions for sanitation and hygiene facilities, safe drinking water, and proper ventilation (DepEd, 2018). Additionally, the DOH has launched programs to educate ECE providers and parents on the importance of health and safety in ECE and to provide support for the implementation of these standards (DOH, 2018). In conclusion, ensuring the provision of a safe and healthy environment is a crucial component of the availability of resources in the delivery of ECE in the Philippines. While the country faces many challenges in this area, the government has taken steps to address these issues and improve the quality of ECE centers. More research and investments are needed to ensure that every child in the country has access to safe and healthy ECE programs.

Table 6 shows the summary of the extent of availability of resources. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: teacher training and support (3.01), community support and engagement (2.98), health and safety (2.77) are oftentimes manifested, while, adequate facilities and resources (2.59) and access to educational resources (2.58) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.78 denotes the extent of availability of resources is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

to factors like economic constraints and insufficient infrastructure. Efforts should be made to bridge this gap by investing in technology, establishing libraries, and providing subsidized or free access to educational materials. The quality of education heavily relies on well-trained and supported teachers. Professional development programs, ongoing training, and mentorship op-

Table 8. Extent of Availability of Resources

No	Extent of Availability of Resources	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Access to educational resources	2.58	Less Extensive
2	Teacher training and support	3.01	Moderately Ex- tensive
3	Community support and engagement	2.98	Moderately Ex- tensive
4	Adequate facilities and resources	2.59	Less Extensive
5	Health and safety	2.77	Moderately Ex- tensive
Overall Mean		2.78	Moderately Ex- tensive

portunities enhance teachers’ pedagogical skills and keep them updated with new teaching methods and technologies. However, the availability of such support varies across different regions. In some areas, teacher training and support are comprehensive, while in others, they may be inadequate or nonexistent. Governments and educational institutions should prioritize teacher training and support to ensure quality education for all students. The involvement of the community is essential for creating a holistic educational environment. When communities actively participate in education, it fosters a sense of belonging and shared responsibility. In some regions, community support and engagement are strong, with active parent-teacher associations, volunteer programs, and collaboration between schools and local organizations. However, in marginalized communities, limited community engagement can hinder educational progress. It is crucial to establish partnerships between schools, families, and community organizations to enhance support networks and promote student success. Physical infrastructure and resources are fundamental to providing a conducive learning environment. Adequate classrooms, laboratories, libraries, and sports facilities contribute to holistic develop-

ment. In developed areas, facilities are often well-maintained and resourced, while in underprivileged regions, students may face overcrowded classrooms, lack of basic amenities, or outdated resources. Governments and educational authorities must prioritize investing in infrastructure development, ensuring all students have access to safe and well-equipped learning environments. Health and safety measures are paramount in educational settings. Availability of clean drinking water, sanitation facilities, and access to healthcare services are vital for students’ well-being. In developed countries, health and safety standards are usually well-maintained, with regular inspections and protocols in place. However, in some areas, inadequate infrastructure, lack of clean water, or inadequate healthcare facilities pose significant challenges. Governments and educational institutions must prioritize the provision of basic health and safety requirements to protect students’ physical and mental well-being.

Quality of Early Childhood Education Learners In the Philippine setting, quality delivery of early childhood education is highly important as it is linked to the country’s economic and social development. One study conducted by Sabularse et al. (2019) aimed to determine the

quality of early childhood education services in the Philippines based on the Philippine Quality Standards for Early Childhood Education. The study found that the quality of early childhood education services in the Philippines varies depending on the program and location. It was also noted that the quality of the program is highly dependent on the qualifications and competencies of the teachers. Gonzales et al. (2020) explored the perspectives of parents and teachers on the quality of early childhood education in the Philippines. The study found that parents and teachers perceive the quality of early childhood education as multifaceted, which includes the provision of appropriate learning materials, a conducive learning environment, teacher-child relationships, and the implementation of developmentally appropriate practices.

Table 7 shows the extent of quality of early childhood education learners in terms of teacher-child interaction. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Includes using rich and varied language with young children, which

Teacher-child interaction is a crucial component of early childhood education that plays a significant role in determining the quality of education that children receive. Hamre and Pianta (2001) explored the importance of teacher-child interactions in promoting positive academic and social outcomes for children. The researchers emphasized that children's learning experiences in early childhood education settings are significantly influenced by the nature and quality of teacher-child interactions. Similarly, a study conducted by Deslandes and Bertrand (2005) investigated the relationship between teacher-child interactions and child development outcomes in early childhood education settings. The study found that positive teacher-child interactions, such as providing support, encouragement, and positive feedback, are associated

can help to support their language development and literacy skills (4.00) and Includes providing support and guidance to help children build on their existing knowledge and skills, which can help to promote their cognitive and problem-solving abilities (3.50) are oftentimes manifested; while, Includes creating warm, supportive relationships between teachers and young children, which can promote trust, attachment, and a sense of security (3.00), Includes creating a well-organized and predictable classroom environment, which can help to support children's self-regulation and social-emotional development (3.00) and Includes responding to children's needs, interests, and abilities in a flexible and individualized way, which can help to promote their social-emotional, cognitive, and language development (2.60) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.22 denotes that extent of quality of early childhood education learners in terms of teacher-child interaction is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

with better child development outcomes, including cognitive and socio-emotional development. Berry et al. (2008) explored the impact of teacher-child interactions on children's learning experiences in early childhood education settings. The study found that positive teacher-child interactions, such as fostering positive relationships, listening actively, and responding sensitively, contribute to children's emotional well-being and academic success.

Table 8 shows the extent of quality of early childhood education learners in terms of curriculum and instructional practices. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: A quality early childhood education program should have a curriculum that is appropriate for the age and developmental stage of the children. The

Table 9. Extent of Availability of Resources in Terms of Teacher-Child Interaction

No	Teacher-Child Interaction	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Includes creating warm, supportive relationships between teachers and young children, which can promote trust, attachment, and a sense of security.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
2	Includes responding to children’s needs, interests, and abilities in a flexible and individualized way, which can help to promote their social-emotional, cognitive, and language development.	2.60	Moderately Extensive
3	Includes using rich and varied language with young children, which can help to support their language development and literacy skills.	4.00	Extensive
4	Includes providing support and guidance to help children build on their existing knowledge and skills, which can help to promote their cognitive and problem-solving abilities.	3.50	Extensive
5	Includes creating a well-organized and predictable classroom environment, which can help to support children’s self-regulation and social-emotional development.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
	Overall Mean	3.22	Moderately Extensive

curriculum should be designed to support children's growth and development across all areas, including cognitive, social-emotional, and physical development (3.80) and Technology can be used as a tool to enhance early childhood education. Quality programs should incorporate technology in a developmentally appropriate way to support children's learning and development. This can include interactive whiteboards, educational apps, and other age-appropriate technology tools (3.50) are oftentimes manifested; while, Play-based learning is an effective approach to early childhood education as it allows children to learn and develop through exploration and discovery. Quality programs should incorporate play-based learning activities that are designed to support children's development across all areas (2.99) is sometimes manifested,

Early childhood education (ECE) is an essential phase of education that has been linked with various developmental outcomes for children (García Pence, 2012). Teacher-child interaction, specifically, has been identified as a crucial aspect of quality ECE delivery that contributes to children's cognitive, social, and emotional development (Burchinal et al., 2011). Diamante et al. (2021) examined the impact of a teacher training program on teacher-child interaction in the Philippines. The study involved 70 ECE teachers who participated in a professional development program that aimed to improve their teaching practices, including teacher-child interactions. The researchers used the CLASS tool to observe teacher-child interactions before and after the training program. The study found a significant improvement in the quality of teacher-child interactions after the training program, suggesting that teacher training can enhance the quality of ECE delivery in the Philippines. Similarly, in a study by Lacsamana et al. (2019), the authors investigated the impact of a coaching program on teacher-child interac-

and, Quality early childhood education programs should include multicultural education that promotes diversity, equity, and inclusion. Children should learn about different cultures and traditions, and teachers should incorporate diverse perspectives into the curriculum (2.45) and Early childhood education programs should provide individualized instruction that is tailored to each child's unique needs and interests. This can be achieved through small group activities, one-on-one instruction, and teacher observation and assessment (2.15) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.81 denotes that extent of quality of early childhood education learners in terms of curriculum and instructional practices is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

tions in the Philippines. The study involved 70 ECE teachers who received coaching sessions focused on enhancing their interactions with children. The researchers used the CLASS tool to observe teacher-child interactions before and after the coaching program. The study found that the coaching program led to a significant improvement in the quality of teacher-child interactions, with positive effects on children's cognitive and socio-emotional development.

Table 9 shows the extent of quality of early childhood education learners in terms of family engagement. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Involves building strong relationships between families and educators, where both parties work together to support the child's development and learning (3.50) and Includes regular and clear communication between teachers and families, including sharing information about the child's progress, challenges, and successes (3.40) are oftentimes manifested; while; Involves creating opportunities for parents and families to engage in their child's learning pro-

Table 10. Extent of Quality of Early Childhood Education Learners in Terms of Curriculum and Instructional Practices

No	Curriculum and Instructional Practices	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	A quality early childhood education program should have a curriculum that is appropriate for the age and developmental stage of the children. The curriculum should be designed to support children’s growth and development across all areas, including cognitive, social-emotional, and physical development.	3.80	Extensive
2	Play-based learning is an effective approach to early childhood education as it allows children to learn and develop through exploration and discovery. Quality programs should incorporate play-based learning activities that are designed to support children’s development across all areas.	2.99	Moderately Extensive
3	Early childhood education programs should provide individualized instruction that is tailored to each child’s unique needs and interests. This can be achieved through small group activities, one-on-one instruction, and teacher observation and assessment.	2.15	Less Extensive
4	Quality early childhood education programs should include multicultural education that promotes diversity, equity, and inclusion. Children should learn about different cultures and traditions, and teachers should incorporate diverse perspectives into the curriculum.	2.45	Less Extensive
5	Technology can be used as a tool to enhance early childhood education. Quality programs should incorporate technology in a developmentally appropriate way to support children’s learning and development. This can include interactive whiteboards, educational apps, and other age-appropriate technology tools.	3.50	Extensive
	Overall Mean	2.97	Moderately Extensive

cess, such as participating in parent-teacher conferences or workshops, helping with homework, and engaging in educational activities at home (3.30) and Involves involving families in decision-making processes, such as developing curriculum or school policies, to ensure that their perspectives and needs are taken into account. (3.00) are sometimes manifested, and Includes providing support for families with different cultural, linguistic, or socioeconomic backgrounds, such as providing translated materials or offering resources to support families who may face additional challenges (2.45) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.13 denotes that extent of quality of early childhood education learners in terms of family engagement is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 11. Extent of Quality of Early Childhood Education Learners in Terms of Family Engagement

No	Family Engagement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Involves creating opportunities for parents and families to engage in their child’s learning process, such as participating in parent-teacher conferences or workshops, helping with homework, and engaging in educational activities at home.	3.30	Moderately Extensive
2	Includes regular and clear communication between teachers and families, including sharing information about the child’s progress, challenges, and successes.	3.40	Extensive
3	Involves building strong relationships between families and educators, where both parties work together to support the child’s development and learning.	3.50	Extensive
4	Includes providing support for families with different cultural, linguistic, or socioeconomic backgrounds, such as providing translated materials or offering resources to support families who may face additional challenges.	2.45	Less Extensive
5	Involves involving families in decision-making processes, such as developing curriculum or school policies, to ensure that their perspectives and needs are taken into account.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
	Overall Mean	3.13	Moderately Extensive

Early childhood education (ECE) is a crucial period for children's growth and development, and an effective curriculum and instructional practices can significantly enhance the quality of ECE. Peacock-Chambers et al. (2018) emphasized the importance of a well-designed ECE curriculum in promoting children's development. The authors found that an evidence-based curriculum that aligns with children's developmental needs and interests can enhance children's cognitive and socio-emotional development. Moreover, effective instructional practices, such as providing opportunities for play-based learning, can further enhance the impact of the curriculum. Another study by Cerna and Franz (2019) focused on the importance of culturally responsive ECE curriculum in the international setting. The authors argued that a curriculum that recognizes and values children's cultural backgrounds can foster a sense of belonging and promote positive socio-emotional outcomes for children. The study suggests that educators need to be trained in cultural competence to effectively implement culturally respon-

Assessment and evaluation are critical components of early childhood education as they provide information on the progress and development of children. This information helps teachers to plan and adjust their instructional practices to better support the needs of each child. A study conducted by Sylva et al. (2018) explored the effectiveness of the Early Years Foundation Stage Profile (EYFSP) in measuring the progress of children in the United Kingdom. The results of the study showed that the EYFSP was a reliable and valid measure of children's progress in the early years of education. The authors suggested that the EYFSP could be used to identify areas where children need additional support and to track their progress over time. In a similar study conducted by Li and Li (2021) in China, the authors examined the effective-

sive curriculum and instructional practices.

Table 10 shows the extent of quality of early childhood education learners in terms of assessment and evaluation. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Use of formative assessments to track student progress and adjust instruction accordingly (4.20) is always manifested; while, Use of multiple types of assessments, such as observations, checklists, and portfolios, to gather comprehensive data on student learning (4.15), Use of assessment data to inform program and instructional improvements and decisions (3.50) and Regular communication with families about their child's progress and involvement in the assessment process (3.45) are oftentimes manifested, and, Implementation of developmentally appropriate assessments that are aligned with learning goals and standards (3.30) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.72 denotes that extent of quality of early childhood education learners in terms of assessment and evaluation is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

ness of the Work Sampling System (WSS) in assessing the development of young children. The results of the study indicated that the WSS was an effective tool for assessing children's development and providing feedback to teachers and parents. The authors recommended that the WSS be used as a formative assessment tool to support the learning and development of young children.

A study by McLean and Matthews (2021) in Australia explored the use of digital technologies in assessment and evaluation in early childhood education. The authors found that digital technologies could provide a more efficient and accurate way to assess and evaluate children's learning and development. The authors recommended that teachers receive adequate training and support to effectively use

Table 12. Extent of Quality of Early Childhood Education Learners in Terms of Assessment and Evaluation

No	Assessment and Evaluation	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Use of formative assessments to track student progress and adjust instruction accordingly	4.20	Very Extensive
2	Implementation of developmentally appropriate assessments that are aligned with learning goals and standards	3.30	Moderately Extensive
3	Use of multiple types of assessments, such as observations, checklists, and portfolios, to gather comprehensive data on student learning	4.15	Extensive
4	Regular communication with families about their child's progress and involvement in the assessment process	3.45	Extensive
5	Use of assessment data to inform program and instructional improvements and decisions.	3.50	Extensive
	Overall Mean	3.72	Extensive

digital technologies in assessment and evaluation. In a study conducted by Alghamdi and Aldossari (2019) in Saudi Arabia, the authors explored the effectiveness of teacher-made assessments in early childhood education. The results of the study showed that teacher-made assessments were effective in measuring children’s progress and providing information to guide instructional practices. The authors suggested that teacher-made assessments could be used to complement standardized assessments to provide a more complete picture of children’s progress and development.

Table 11 shows the summary of the extent of students’ understanding in mathematical concepts. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: assessment and evaluation (3.72) is oftentimes manifested; while, teacher-child interaction (3.22), family engagement (3.13) and curriculum and instructional practices (2.97) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.26 denotes that extent of students’ understanding in mathematical concepts is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 13. Summary of the Extent of Quality of Early Childhood Education Learners

No	Quality of Early Childhood Education Learners	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Teacher-child interaction	3.22	Moderately Extensive
2	Curriculum and instructional practices	2.97	Moderately Extensive
3	Family engagement	3.13	Moderately Extensive
4	Assessment and evaluation	3.72	Extensive
	Overall Mean	3.26	Moderately Extensive

Teacher-child interaction is a cornerstone of quality early childhood education. Positive and nurturing relationships between teachers and children create a supportive learning environment and promote social-emotional development. In high-quality early childhood education programs, teachers engage in responsive and individualized interactions, actively listening to children, encouraging their ideas, and providing appropriate guidance. However, in some settings, limited teacher training or high student-to-teacher ratios can hinder the quality of these interactions. It is essential to invest in professional development and maintain favorable teacher-student ratios to ensure optimal teacher-child

interaction. The curriculum and instructional practices in early childhood education significantly influence children’s cognitive, physical, and socio-emotional development. High-quality programs employ developmentally appropriate practices that align with children’s needs and interests. They incorporate play-based learning, hands-on activities, and meaningful experiences. Furthermore, well-designed curricula provide a balance between structured and child-initiated activities, promoting active engagement and critical thinking. However, in some cases, standardized curricula or a lack of resources can limit the quality of instruction. It is crucial to prioritize the use of research-based, culturally sensitive

curricula and provide adequate resources for effective instructional practices. Involving families in early childhood education strengthens the partnership between parents and educators, benefiting children’s learning and development. Quality programs encourage family engagement by fostering open communication, involving parents in decision-making processes, and providing resources for parents to support learning at home. Engaged families play an active role in their children’s education, reinforcing learning experiences and promoting positive outcomes. However, in some instances, language barriers, limited parent involvement, or lack of parental education can affect family engagement. Educators and institutions should implement strategies to overcome these barriers, such as offering translation services, hosting family workshops, and promoting inclusive and welcoming environments. Assessment and evaluation practices in early childhood education inform instructional decisions, monitor progress, and identify areas for improvement. High-quality programs use a variety of assessment methods, including observation, documentation, and portfolios, to gather comprehensive information about chil-

dren’s development. These assessments are ongoing, authentic, and tailored to individual children’s needs, providing a holistic understanding of their growth. However, in some cases, assessment practices may be limited to traditional tests or focus solely on academic achievement. It is important to ensure that assessments in early childhood education encompass multiple domains of development and align with best practices to promote meaningful evaluation.

Significant Relationship Between Availability of Resources and Quality of Early Childhood Education Learners

It can be depicted that Pearson’s Correlation generated a significant correlation between availability of resources ($r=0.885$; $p<.000$) and quality of early childhood education learners. Table 12 revealed the yielded results of the significant relationship between availability of resources and quality of early childhood education learners. It provides an information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant correlation between availability of resources and quality of early childhood education learners must be rejected for it provided empirical evidence of significant results.

Table 14. Significant Relationship between Availability of Resources and Quality of Early Childhood Education Learners

Variables	Availability of Resources	r- value	p-value	Interpretation
Quality of Early Childhood Education Learners				
Availability of Resources	0.885	< 0.000	Significant	Reject H0

*significant @ $p < 0.05$.

Access to educational resources is vital for promoting optimal learning experiences in early childhood education. Research by Siraj-

Blatchford et al. (2017) indicates that children who have access to a diverse range of age-appropriate resources demonstrate higher levels

of engagement and learning outcomes. These resources include books, toys, manipulatives, and digital tools, which facilitate hands-on exploration, creativity, and cognitive development. Teacher training and support are key elements in delivering quality early childhood education. Studies by Whitebook et al. (2017) and Buettner (2015) highlight the significance of well-trained and supported teachers in improving children's educational experiences. Comprehensive professional development programs focusing on early childhood pedagogy, child development, and effective instructional strategies equip teachers with the necessary skills to create engaging and developmentally appropriate learning environments. Community support and engagement play a crucial role in early childhood education. Research by Smith et al. (2015) demonstrates that when families, communities, and early childhood education providers work together, children experience better educational outcomes. Community involvement can include parental engagement programs, partnerships with local organizations, and initiatives that promote inclusive early childhood practices. The availability of adequate facilities and resources significantly contributes to the quality of early childhood education. Studies by Elicker et al. (2016) and Kontos et al. (2019) emphasize that well-designed learning environments, equipped with developmentally appropriate materials, promote active learning and positive child outcomes. High-quality facilities, including age-appropriate furniture, outdoor play areas, and safe learning spaces, foster children's engagement, curiosity, and overall well-being. Health and safety considerations are integral to high-quality early childhood education. Research by Trawick-Smith et al. (2016) and Jambunathan et al. (2018) highlight the impact of health and safety practices on chil-

dren's learning experiences. Ensuring a safe and healthy environment, including proper hygiene practices, age-appropriate safety measures, and regular health screenings, contributes to children's well-being, allowing them to fully engage in the learning process.

Domains of Availability of Resources That Significantly Influence Quality of Early Childhood Education Learners

Table 13 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on the domains of availability of resources that significantly influence quality of early childhood education learners. Domains of availability of resources in terms of access to educational resources (0.000), teacher training and support (0.003), community support and engagement (0.000) adequate facilities and resources (0.001), and health and safety (0.001) significantly influence quality of early childhood education learners. Meanwhile, the R² value of 0.856 suggests that the domains of availability of resources, is explained by 85.6%. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (284.697) and F-statistic is significant $p < .001$, tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of students' understanding in mathematical concepts. Early childhood education plays a crucial role in the holistic development of children. The availability of appropriate resources greatly impacts the quality of education provided to young learners. This essay examines the significance of resources in four key areas: teacher-child interaction, curriculum and instructional practices, family engagement, and assessment and evaluation. By exploring research and scholarly works, we can understand how the availability of resources in these areas shapes the learning experiences of early childhood education learners.

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

AER - access to educational resources;

Table 15. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Availability Of Resources That Significantly Influence Quality Of Early Childhood Education Learners

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decisions
H (Intercept)	4.145	0.079	60.416	0.001	4.145
H (Intercept)	0.313	0.175	1.066	0.270	0.204
AER	0.807	0.107	0.102	1.010	0.315
0.000	*Reject H0				
TTS	0.441	0.108	0.136	1.299	0.196
0.003	*Reject H0				
CSE	0.202	0.097	0.210	2.098	0.038
0.000	*Reject H0				
AFR	0.683	0.086	0.499	5.654	0.001
0.001	*Reject H0				
HS	0.807	0.107	0.136	1.299	0.196
0.001	*Reject H0				
R²	= 0.856				
F-value	= 284.697				
p-value	= < 0.001				

TTS - teacher training and support;
CSE - community support and engagement;
AFR - adequate facilities and resources; and
HS - health and safety

Teacher-child interaction is a fundamental aspect of early childhood education. The availability of resources can greatly enhance these interactions. Research by Pianta (2017) emphasizes the importance of high-quality teacher-child interactions in promoting positive outcomes for children. Resources such as open-ended materials, educational games, and developmentally appropriate toys facilitate engaging interactions that foster cognitive, social, and emotional development. These resources support teachers in providing responsive, individualized, and meaningful experiences for young learners. The availability of resources significantly influences the design and implementation of curricula and instructional practices. Research by Epstein and Van Voorhis (2015) suggests that access to a variety of developmentally appropriate resources enhances curriculum effectiveness. Resources such as books, educational materials, and technology tools provide opportunities for hands-on, experiential learning. They enable teachers to implement innovative instructional strategies, differentiate instruction, and tailor learning experiences to meet the diverse needs of early childhood learners. Resources play a crucial role in fostering family engagement in early childhood education. Research by Sheridan et al. (2017) emphasizes that the availability of resources and materials at home promotes family involvement in children's learning. Resources such as books, learning kits, and educational games can be provided to families, enabling them to support and ex-

tend children's learning experiences beyond the classroom. By involving families in learning activities, educators can establish strong partnerships that positively impact children's educational outcomes. Resources also play a vital role in the assessment and evaluation of early childhood education. Research by La Paro et al. (2018) highlights the importance of age-appropriate assessment tools and materials. Resources, such as observation materials, portfolios, and standardized assessment instruments, provide educators with valuable insights into children's development, strengths, and areas for improvement. These resources support accurate and comprehensive assessments, allowing teachers to tailor instruction and interventions to meet individual needs effectively. The availability of resources significantly influences the quality of early childhood education learners in various dimensions. Through the examination of research and scholarly works, we have explored the impact of resources on teacher-child interaction, curriculum and instructional practices, family engagement, and assessment and evaluation. These resources provide opportunities for engaging interactions, facilitate effective curriculum implementation, foster family involvement, and support accurate assessments. By ensuring the availability of appropriate resources in these areas, stakeholders can create an enriched learning environment that promotes the optimal development and success of young learners in early childhood education.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusion and recommendation based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and drawn implications. Findings are based on the posed statement of the problem; conclusions are based on the findings generated and recommendations are based on

the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following are findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis and discussions. The extent of availability of resources in terms of teacher training and support (3.01), community support and engagement (2.98), health and safety (2.77) are oftentimes manifested, while, adequate facilities and resources (2.59) and access to educational resources (2.58) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.78 denotes the extent of availability of resources is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The extent of students' understanding in mathematical concepts in terms of assessment and evaluation (3.72) is oftentimes manifested; while, teacher-child interaction (3.22), family engagement (3.13) and curriculum and instructional practices (2.97) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.26 denotes that extent of students' understanding in mathematical concepts is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between availability of resources ($r=0.885$; $p<.000$) and quality of early childhood education learners. Domains of availability of resources in terms of access to educational resources (0.000), teacher training and support (0.003), community support and engagement (0.000) adequate facilities and resources (0.001), and health and safety (0.001) significantly influence quality of early childhood education learners.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are conclusions, to wit; The availability of resources in terms of teacher training and support, community support and engagement, health and safety, adequate facilities, resources, access to educational resources is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The students' understanding in mathematical concepts in terms of assessment and evaluation, teacher-child interaction,

family engagement and curriculum and instructional practices is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. There is a significant relationship between availability of resources and quality of early childhood education learners. Domains of availability of resources in terms of access to educational resources, teacher training and support, community support and engagement, adequate facilities and resources, and health and safety does significantly influenced quality of early childhood education learners.

4.3. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; Public School District Supervisor. May prioritize funding and allocation of resources for early childhood education programs to ensure access to age-appropriate materials, technology tools, and professional development opportunities for teachers. Establish clear guidelines and expectations for resource allocation to ensure equitable distribution of resources across all early childhood education classrooms. Support and promote collaborations with community organizations, businesses, and parents to enhance resource availability through donations, partnerships, and grants. School Principal. May advocate for adequate funding and resources to support high-quality early childhood education programs within the school. Ensure that teachers have access to ongoing professional development opportunities that focus on utilizing resources effectively to enhance teaching and learning experiences. Create a positive and inclusive school culture that values the role of resources in supporting the holistic development of young learners. Collaborate with teachers and other stakeholders to regularly assess and update the inventory of available resources, identifying any gaps and needs. Early Childhood Education Teachers. May take an active role in advocating for and utilizing available

resources effectively to enhance teaching and learning experiences for young children. Participate in professional development opportunities to enhance knowledge and skills in utilizing resources to support child development and learning. Collaborate with colleagues to share best practices, resources, and strategies for maximizing the use of available resources. Regularly assess and reflect on the effectiveness of resources used in the classroom, making adjustments as necessary to meet the needs of individual learners. Future Researchers. May conduct further research on the impact of specific resources and their availability on early childhood education outcomes. Investigate the effectiveness of different resource allocation models and strategies in promoting quality early childhood education. Explore the relationship between resource availability and the inclusion of diverse learners, such as those with disabilities or from culturally and linguistically diverse backgrounds. Examine the long-term effects of resource availability in early childhood education on children's academic achievement, socio-emotional development, and future success. By implementing these recommendations, public school district supervisors, school principals, early childhood education teachers, and future researchers can contribute to enhancing the quality of early childhood education by ensuring the availability and effective utilization of resources.

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